

**FRACTURE INITIATION IN PARTICLE HARDENED MATERIALS
WITH HIGH VOLUME FRACTION**

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ABSTRACT

Understanding of the fracture initiation process is especially important to developing improved materials which contain a high volume fraction of reinforcement particles, such as metal matrix composites. In this paper, the theoretical and experimental background for void nucleation by either particle/matrix decohesion or particle cracking is reviewed, highlighting the roles of matrix microstructure, interface bonding, and the particle characteristics. Experimental results on both Al-SiC composite and Al-Si model systems are presented as illustration of key factors such as particle clustering. Future work directed at further delineating the roles of the various microstructural features in the fracture initiation process is outlined.

INTRODUCTION

The study of fracture processes in particle-containing materials has been an area of continuing research for a number of years. For metallic materials, the study has tended to focus on particle volume fractions generally ≤ 0.1 and very frequently below 0.01, since this is the typical volume fraction of second phase particles (constituents, inclusions, etc.) in many commercial alloys. Increasing interest in metals containing higher volume fractions of particles has been the result of the development of metal matrix composites, in which typically stiff, strong, and brittle ceramic reinforcements are added in order to tailor the mechanical and physical properties of the material, such as stiffness, strength, wear resistance, thermal expansion coefficient, etc., to meet the property requirements for the particular application. Along with the improvements in these properties, however, comes reduction of fracture-related properties, such as ductility and fracture toughness, which currently limits application of these materials in many structural applications. Thus, it is of interest to better understand the micromechanisms of fracture in these materials on a combined microstructure and mechanics basis in order to develop maximum fracture resistance.

Of particular commercial interest is the case of reinforcement by

particles having a roughly equiaxed geometry, since they can be produced with relatively isotropic properties using existing metalworking equipment and processes. These materials have also been the subject of theoretical study, with fracture processes being considered primarily in terms of extensions of existing fracture models for the lower volume fracture materials [1,2]. The bulk of the models address the process of nucleation of voids formed at or near the particle/matrix interface by decohesion or particle cracking, growth, and finally coalescence. Basically, these models propose that voids are nucleated at some (typically fixed) nucleation strain, grow under the applied stress and strain fields until they reach a critical size, and subsequently coalesce through failure of the matrix ligaments. In general, these models concentrate on the processes of void growth once voids have formed, and for low volume fraction materials, can provide good agreement with experimental observations [3-5]. Extension of these models to the higher volume fraction materials has been less successful [1,2].

It would, in fact, be surprising if models based primarily on void growth mechanisms would effectively predict the behavior in high volume fraction particle hardened materials. Simple void growth models (e.g., Brown and Embury [3]) indicate that the coalescence of voids will occur when the void length is equal to the interparticle spacing. This model concentrates on the amount of growth strain required before the voids reach the critical size for linkage. With increasing volume fraction of particles for a given mean particle size, the interparticle spacing decreases and the amount of growth strain required also decreases. Assuming a uniform particle size and distribution, the particle volume fraction at which the growth strain becomes zero is calculated to be ~0.16. In real materials with random particle distributions, areas of local volume fraction greater than the mean value will be found, suggesting that the critical condition could be reached in materials with even lower mean values of particle volume fraction than the 0.16 level. If the possibility of clustered microstructures is considered, an even more exaggerated effect might be expected. Experimentally, the occurrence of stable voids in "commercial" MMC materials is rare [6,7]. This suggests that optimizing microstructures based primarily on void growth considerations (which is effective for lower volume fraction materials) may not produce the desired results in these high volume fraction materials. This points to the criticality of considering the details of the void nucleation process.

Void Nucleation Models

The void nucleation process has received attention in a number of investigations [5,8-11]. From this work, there is substantial disagreement on the role of various microstructural parameters on void nucleation. Much of this can be attributed to the scale of the microstructure considered and whether the treatment involved dislocation of continuum mechanics.

It is generally agreed that two criteria must be met for a void to nucleate. The first is that a certain amount of energy must be supplied by the deformation process such that the increase in surface energy resulting from either a decohesion or particle fracture process can be compensated. The so-called critical energy criteria is considered to be a necessary but not sufficient condition for nucleation for particle sizes larger than ~1 μm .

A critical interfacial stress criteria must also be satisfied. Argon et al. [10] express this condition based on continuum analysis as:

$$\sigma_{rr} = Y(\bar{\epsilon}_p) + \sigma_m$$

where σ_{rr} is the radial stress,

$Y(\bar{\epsilon}_p)$ is the work hardened matrix stress, and

σ_m is the imposed hydrostatic stress component.

Fisher and Gurland [9] point out that the most appropriate approach is that of a combined critical energy and critical interfacial stress criteria for void nucleation.

Stress state can have an important influence on the void nucleation process, with higher degrees of triaxiality resulting in void nucleation at lower strains. The hydrostatic stress component is added to the stress generated by matrix flow in terms of approaching the critical interfacial stress. The work of Brownrigg et al. [12], employing varying levels of imposed hydrostatic pressure during the deformation of a spheroidized 1045 steel, clearly demonstrates the important role of the hydrostatic pressure component.

Another fracture model that has been recently proposed by You et al. [7] involves a fracture process in which the matrix fails, followed by fracturing or decohesion of the particles as the final rather than the initial step in the fracture process. It is envisioned that void nucleation occurs in the matrix as a result of the high levels of plastic constraint imposed by the presence of the second phase particles. Since this model is based on the results from a single composite system, further study will be necessary to test its range of applicability.

Microstructural Factors in Void Nucleation

Focusing on the void nucleation process, a number of microstructural factors must be considered. Two important variables are the matrix yield strength and work hardening behavior. The primary role of increasing yield strength is to activate a greater number of potential nucleation sites by causing more particle matrix interfaces to reach their decohesion stress or increasing the frequency of particle cracking. Work hardening behavior has a similar effect in nucleation, with higher work hardening resulting in greater stress in the vicinity of the particle. This is in contrast to the role of work hardening in the void growth process, where higher work hardening levels restrict the growth of stable voids and increase strain to fracture and toughness.

Another variable of importance is the strength of the bond at the interface. It is generally agreed that the stronger this bond, the greater resistance to void nucleation exists. The modeling work of Fisher and Gurland [9] and the experimental data of Fischmeister et al. [13] have demonstrated the effect of interfacial bond strength. A secondary effect of bond strength will be the relative tendency for particle cracking vs. decohesion. It is expected that as the bond strength increases, greater stress can be transferred to the particle prior to interface decohesion. If this stress is sufficiently large, particle cracking may occur prior to

interface debonding. The work of Evensen and Verk [14] has suggested that particle cracking as the mechanism of void nucleation might have a deleterious effect of subsequent growth and coalescence (relative to the particle/matrix decohesion mechanism) due to the increased stress concentration produced by the crack.

The question of particle size effect in the void nucleation process continues to be controversial. Most of the foregoing discussion was based on analyses done and appropriate to isolated particles in an infinite matrix. From these results, particle size should not be a significant factor in the nucleation of voids. Yet, certain experimental programs have shown a particle size effect, while others have not. In many cases, these results are influenced by the size and volume fraction of the particles. For small particles at low volume fractions where dislocation models are appropriate, a particle size effect is expected and observed [11]. For larger particles where continuum analyses are appropriate, analysis predicts no particle size effect, which has been most commonly observed, at least in the case of decohesion-related nucleation at low volume fractions [15]. For materials where the particles fracture, however, a particle size effect would be anticipated. If this is the case, Griffith fracture behavior would predict a decreasing nucleation strain with increasing particle size due to the greater probability for finding a critical sized flaw which would fail under lower applied stresses.

This situation changes when particles are of a sufficiently high volume fraction that the stress fields interact, typically at yield for materials with volume fractions greater than ~ 0.1 [10]. It has been demonstrated experimentally that void nucleation occurs preferentially in regions of the microstructure which exhibit the largest local volume fractions of particles, due to the increased stress concentration at the interface in these areas [5,8,10]. High local volume fractions can conceptually be thought of as larger than average particles spaced a smaller than average distance apart. This gives rise to an observed "particle size effect" which may more correctly be classified as a local volume fraction effect.

Recently, the need to account for the nonuniform nature of the second phase particle distribution for even low volume fraction materials has been shown. Thomson and Hancock [16] recognized that even in the Swedish iron samples containing ~ 0.01 volume fraction of iron oxide particles they evaluated, the key aspect with regard to nucleation was the tendency for a locally higher volume fraction of particles to exist which would serve as the area in which initiation occurs at the lowest strain. This supports the contention of LeRoy et al. [5] and Embury [17], who point out that it is incorrect to model of the nucleation process as a fixed strain event rather than one in which nucleation first occurs in local areas of highest particle concentration, followed by subsequent nucleation at higher strains in other regions of the material. Therefore, a knowledge of the distribution of nucleation strains, which are dependent on the particular microstructure, is required.

In summary, the process of void nucleation appears to be the critical one (relative to void growth) in the fracture of materials with particle volume fractions greater than ~ 0.1 . For these high volume fraction materials, the characteristics of matrix yield strength and work hardening desired may be quite different than those in lower volume fraction

materials in which fracture is controlled predominantly by void growth. The role of the particle characteristics will be primarily in their distribution, with a secondary intrinsic size effect with regard to the tendency for particle cracking vs. particle/matrix decohesion.

Questions still remain regarding the details of the void nucleation process, especially in terms of the various microstructural parameters which affect it. It is the primary purpose of the work described below to begin to systematically study these parameters.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Two types of particle hardened materials are being considered in this work. The first is a metal matrix composite material consisting of an Al-7% Zn-2% Mg-2% Cu-0.14% Zr matrix alloy (designated MB78) produced via powder metallurgy, reinforced by SiC particulate. Experimental variables are the mean Al-to-SiC particle size ratio (0.24:1 and 0.7:1) and the nominal SiC particle volume fraction (0.15 to 0.2). These materials were produced by blending and consolidating the powders, followed by extrusion to either a 1-inch diameter rod or 1 X 3-inch bar. Thermal treatments were applied to produce underaged, peak aged, and overaged tempers in order to study matrix microstructure effects.

Synthetically produced metal matrix composite materials are sufficiently complex materials that understanding of the fundamental microstructural mechanisms controlling the fracture process is difficult. A simpler system was desired which would allow more control over particle size and distribution as well as elimination of the extraneous second phases which complicate behavior. The system chosen for this work was the Al-Si system, in which elemental Si particles are formed upon solidification. By utilizing a strip casting process, sheet materials of ~0.25 inch thickness with roughly spherical Si particles of <1 μm in diameter were produced. These structures were then coarsened for times of 0.25 h (Treatment A), 24 h (Treatment C), and 421 h (Treatment E) at 565°C to provide a range of particle sizes, without significant changes in particle size distributions. Initial work focused on lower volume fraction materials ranging from 0.02-0.11. These lower volume fractions, along with the low strength Al matrix, provided for relatively high ductilities compared to the MB78-SiC materials, thus allowing easier study of the void development as a function of strain.

Experimental Methods

Quantitative characterization of the particle size and spatial distribution is critical to an understanding of the fracture process. Alcoa Laboratories is fortunate to have an automated image analysis system attached to an ISI 100 scanning electron microscope plus associated computer software which allows determination of metallographic parameters such as local volume fraction, nearest and near neighbor spacing, and anisotropy of the particle distribution, providing data beyond the typical mean particle size, spacing, and volume fraction. The analysis approach involves dividing the microstructure into Dirichlet cells, with each cell comprised of the particle and that area of matrix closer to the particular

particle than any other. An example of a tessellated microstructure is shown in Figure 1. Through this construction, the metallographic parameters discussed above are readily determined [18]. Both the MB78-SiC metal matrix composites and the Al-Si binary alloys were characterized on a planar section transverse to either the extrusion direction (MB78-SiC composite) or the casting direction (Al-Si).

Figure 1. Example of tessellated microstructure from Reference 18.

Mechanical testing for the MB78-SiC composites consisted of standard uniaxial tensile testing of 4-mm diameter round bars stressed at a crosshead speed of 0.005 s^{-1} in the direction of the extrusion and short rod fracture toughness testing in the T-L orientation. The latter provides a toughness indicator only. Correlation with valid K_{Ic} below $\sim 25 \text{ ksi } \sqrt{\text{in}}$ is good, while above this level the short rod test overpredicts toughness by $\sim 10\%$.

The Al-Si alloys were also subjected to uniaxial tensile testing under similar conditions as the MB78-SiC composites. In this case, a 3.175-mm diameter bar oriented with the stressing direction parallel to the casting direction was used. In selected cases, acoustic emission monitoring of the tensile tests was carried out in an effort to provide a more complete description of the void nucleation process. The measurements were made with a total gain of 110 db and bandpass of 100–300 kHz employing a resonant-type transducer. Noise characterization and preloading of the grips ensured that the monitored signal was not noise generated by the testing apparatus.

Failed tensile specimens from both the MB78-SiC and Al-Si alloys were longitudinally sectioned in order to study the fracture process as a function of distance from the fracture plane.

RESULTSMB78 Matrix-SiC Reinforced Materials

Tensile and short rod fracture toughness information were developed for the MB78-SiC composites as a function of particle size ratio (PSR) and SiC particle volume fraction. Figure 2 shows the results for a nominal SiC volume fraction of 0.2 in MB78 for two PSR values and the range of matrix microstructures generated through the various artificial aging treatments. From this figure, it is apparent that PSR has a significant effect on the attainable property combinations, with the larger PSR of 0.7:1 producing a better combination of properties than the 0.24:1 PSR. In addition, the matrix properties have a strong effect, with decreasing toughness as strength increases upon aging, followed by little or no recovery of the toughness property even with the significant reductions in strength occurring upon overaging. The same trends are seen in the composites with a nominal SiC volume fraction of 0.15, although the location of the strength-toughness curves is displaced to higher values.

Figure 2. Strength-toughness relationships for MB78-SiC composites.

Longitudinal metallographic sections were taken from the failed tensile specimens in order to study the details of the fracture process. Figures 3a and 3b show regions at the fracture surface for the MB78-SiC composites with PSR = 0.24:1 and 0.7:1, respectively. In the material with a smaller SiC particle size (Figure 3a), greater clustering of the reinforcement particles is seen. The fracture appears to selectively seek out these clustered regions. The larger particles in composite shown in Figure 3b are qualitatively less clustered, and the fracture path is more random in nature. No evidence of stable voids is observed in either material, as suggested previously [6,7].

Figure 3. Longitudinal sections near tensile fracture surface for (a) PSR = 0.24:1 and (b) PSR = 0.7:1 MB78-W + 20% SiC.

Figure 4. Two examples of void nucleation in regions of clustered SiC particles [19].

Additional evidence for the importance of regions of clustered particles on the nucleation process is seen in Figures 4a and 4b. Using

double blunt-notched bend bars, Lewandowski [19] was able to isolate nucleation events in an MB78-SiC composite. The micrographs in Figure 4 indicate preferential nucleation in regions of high local volume fraction of particles, as anticipated from continuum models [10].

The quantitative metallographic approach described in the previous section was employed to quantify the degree of clustering in these materials as a function of the experimental variables of particle size ratio and nominal SiC Particle volume fraction. For each material, approximately 1000 particles were analyzed. Particular attention was focused on the distribution of local volume fractions of particles in each material in an effort to delineate the tendency for particle clustering. This was done by plotting the probability of occurrence of a local volume fraction f normalized by the mean local volume fraction, \bar{f} against the ratio f/\bar{f} for the measured particle distributions and comparing this to expected values for a randomly distributed particle population. Greater deviation from the line representing randomly distributed particles indicates increasingly nonrandom distributions. Figure 5 presents the data for the four MB78-SiC composite variables. The deviation of the data for the metal matrix composites in the high local volume fraction range shows a tendency for preferential clustering of the SiC particles, with increasing tendency for clustering with increasing nominal volume fraction and decreasing particle size ratio.

Figure 5. $P(f/\bar{f})$ vs. f/\bar{f} for MB78-SiC composites.

Al-Si Alloys

Table 1 lists the metallographic parameters for the Al-Si alloys examined. A sizable range in both particle size and volume fraction was

achieved. Metallographic examination of the roll cast Al-Si alloys demonstrated a generally random distribution of Si particles except near the centerline regions, where preferential clustering of the particles occurred as a result of the casting process. The clustered areas consist of discrete particles of mean size similar to that of the unclustered regions. These particles macroscopically form rod-shaped regions of clustering, although the individual particles have a generally equiaxed shape. A representative three-dimensional micrograph is shown in Figure 6.

TABLE 1
Quantitative metallographic parameters for roll cast Al-Si alloys.

Nominal Si Level (wt%)	Treatment A		Treatment C		Treatment E	
	Mean A_f	Mean Particle Dia (μm)	Mean A_f	Mean Particle Dia (μm)	Mean A_f	Mean Particle Dia (μm)
3	0.026	0.80	0.021	2.1	0.020	4.8
5	0.042	0.91	0.049	3.2	0.044	5.2
7	0.060	0.97	0.062	2.6	0.074	5.5
10	0.083	0.92	0.107	3.2	0.106	5.5

Figure 6. Micrograph of Al-7% Si alloy, Treatment C, illustrating typical clustering pattern in roll cast alloys.

Uniaxial tensile data, including tensile strength, yield strength, elongation in 12.7 mm, and reduction area, is shown in Table 2. These show general trends of increasing strength and decreasing ductility with increasing Si particle volume fraction. Strength is slightly decreased with increasing particle size for a given nominal Si volume fraction, while ductility is relatively unaffected.

Acoustic emission monitoring of samples containing a nominal Si content of 7% during the tensile testing indicated different results depending on particle size. For the smaller particle size of the Treatment A specimens, no peaks indicative of particle cracking were observed. The Treatment C and Treatment E specimens did show evidence of particle cracking, typically beginning at relatively small strains in the 2-3% range. Fractographic evaluation suggested that particle/matrix decohesion was the dominant mode of void initiation in the Treatment A sample while particle cracking occurs in the larger particle Treatment C and E samples.

TABLE 2
Uniaxial tensile properties for roll cast Al-Si alloys.

Nominal Si Level (wt%)	Treatment A			Treatment C			Treatment E		
	UTS (MPa)	TYS (MPa)	Reduction of Area (%)	UTS (MPa)	TYS (MPa)	Reduction of Area (%)	UTS (MPa)	TYS (MPa)	Reduction of Area (%)
3	148	71	66	142	68	56	138	70	67
5	161	66	46	156	66	50	148	65	53
7	200	85	48	164	79	43	151	70	46
10	216	97	48	182	87	42	173	83	28

Figure 7. Longitudinal section near tensile fracture surface of Al-7% Si, Treatment C, illustrating preferential particle cracking in clustered region.

Metallographic sections along the stressing direction of the tensile specimens demonstrated that fracture nucleation, which in this case of the Treatment C and E samples was the result of particle cracking, occurs preferentially in regions of clustered particles. Figure 7 illustrates an example of this observation.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Comparison of the mechanical property data for the MB78-SiC composite in Figure 2 and the results of the metallographic analysis summarized in Figure 5 are consistent with the hypothesis that particle clustering may play a significant role in the fracture initiation process in high volume fraction materials. Due to the fact that the particle clustering is greater in the materials with smaller SiC particles, these data do not allow determination of whether there is an intrinsic particle size effect or not. The data also does not establish a casual link between particle clustering and preferential void nucleation. We will attempt to establish this link through the combined use of tensile testing under conditions of high imposed pressures similar to Reference 12 and acoustic emission monitoring. The high imposed pressures will allow reduction of the triaxiality of the macrostress state and permit some stable growth of nucleated voids. The acoustic emission monitoring will be used to identify nucleation events to indicate when metallographic sectioning for confirmation is indicated.

In the Al-Si alloys examined to date, both the lower particle volume fractions and highly ductile matrix make them less nucleation controlled and more growth controlled. This is apparent from the relatively large strains which can be achieved after void nucleation at relatively low strains as indicated by the acoustic emission monitoring.

In an effort to examine the role of particle size and volume fraction, reduction of area values were converted to ductility values ($\ln A_0/A_f$) and plotted as a function of the measured Si particle volume fraction in Figure 8. For comparison, the predictions of the Brown and Embury [3] and Evensen and Verk [14] models for a fixed nucleation strain of 0.1 are plotted as the solid lines. The results follow the general trend of lower ductility with high volume fraction of particles. For the lower volume fractions, behavior follows the Evensen and Verk model, which is based on a void nucleation mechanism by particle cracking which accelerates subsequent growth due to the presence of a sharp crack. With increasing volume fraction, however, there appears to be a particle size dependent shift towards the Brown and Embury prediction, which is based on void nucleation by particle/matrix decohesion and subsequent growth. This shift occurs at the lowest volume fraction for the smallest Si particle sizes (Treatment A) and not at all for the larger particle size materials (Treatment E). One possible explanation for this behavior is that as the interparticle spacing decreases with increasing volume fraction for a given particle size, the void growth and coalescence become less dependent on the mode of void nucleation. This is a potentially significant observation which will be pursued further.

It is not yet clear what role the preferential void nucleation exhibited in regions of high local volume fraction of Si particles (Figure 7) has on the ultimate ductility, although modeling work suggests that it would be deleterious. More important to this work is improved

Figure 8. $\ln A_o/A_f$ vs. Si particle volume fraction in comparison with theoretical models.

understanding of how microstructure influences the void nucleation process. As such, the Al-Si alloys discussed in this paper provide a base for further study of materials with higher volume fractions and stronger, less ductile matrices. We anticipate that higher particle volume fractions can be generated through rapid solidification procedures, while stronger matrices can be produced through ternary alloying additions such as Mg and Cu which can significantly increase the matrix flow stress and modify its work hardening behavior without markedly influencing the characteristics of the Si particles.

In conclusion, the work described in this paper (and its extension) is intended to better understand the role of microstructure in the fracture initiation process, with special attention to particle hardened materials with high volume fractions. Experimental and theoretical work suggest that the void nucleation process is of critical importance, which has been further verified here. We have further shown that attention to the details of the fracture initiation process, such as quantification of particle clustering, is required to gain further knowledge. Subsequent work will approach the key microstructural parameters in a systematic manner in an effort to provide the quantitative understanding required to develop improved materials.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge Richard Borland, John Liu, and Carol George of the Alcoa Laboratories for assistance in the acquisition

and analysis of the quantitative metallographic data. We also wish to recognize valuable discussions with Drs. James Williams and Anthony Thompson of Carnegie-Mellon University, and the assistance of Dr. Steve Carpenter of the University of Denver in the acoustic emission monitoring.

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